

March 4th, 2026

To: Prof. Martha Estela Trujillo Toledo
Editor-in-Chief
& Dr. Praveen Rahi, Editor
International Journal of Systematic and
Evolutionary Microbiology
Re: IJSEM-S-25-00665 Rebuttal

Dear Editors,

Thank you for the opportunity to prepare this rebuttal to the inaccurate and, in several instances, unfair peer review of our manuscript entitled “***Candidatus Phytoplasma zaeae*: community-driven species delineation of the maize bushy stunt phytoplasma, a *Dalbulus*-transmitted corn pathogen confined to the Americas.**”

During the revisions of the manuscript, we went well beyond cosmetic changes and performed additional analyses that directly address the core taxonomic concern raised by both reviewers. In particular, we expanded the genome-wide average nucleotide identity (ANI) analyses to include **all 20 publicly available genomes of ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’-related strains**. This comprehensive comparison shows that **20% exhibit <95% ANI relative to ‘*Ca. P. zaeae*’,** thereby meeting the threshold defined in the 2022 guidelines of Bertaccini et al. for recognizing a distinct ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species. These new results are now fully documented in the revised manuscript (updated **Table S6** and new **Figure S1**) and, together with the ecological evidence summarized under Rule c of the IRPCM guidelines, provide a clear and consistent framework supporting the delineation of ‘*Ca. P. zaeae*’ as a new taxon. All the changes made in the revised manuscript are in **green**, and we are attaching a marked version of the manuscript.

We also wish to be transparent about the nature of the review process. Responding to Reviewer 1, in particular, has been extremely difficult. The annotated PDF contained **165 individual comments and edits**, a substantial number of which were not aimed at improving the science but were borderline offensive, unnecessarily personal, or dismissive, in addition to many scientifically inaccurate. **We have highlighted the most problematic of these in red within our rebuttal for ease of reference.** Despite the huge volume of remarks, very few comments translated into substantive, constructive changes to the manuscript. As we explain point by point below, **the vast majority of the scientific criticism was either technically incorrect, inconsistent with current phytoplasma taxonomy and genomics, or unsupported by the cited literature.** Consequently, the core data, analyses, and conclusions of our study remain unchanged.

We feel compelled to situate this experience within a broader structural context. Phytoplasma taxonomy, and the history of maize bushy stunt in particular, has been shaped for decades by a **colonial model of research**, in which scientists from developed countries travel to Latin America, collect samples, and build careers and taxonomic frameworks with limited or no substantive involvement of local researchers (See references below). Maize bushy stunt is emblematic of this dynamic. For many years, work on this pathogen was conducted largely without leadership from Latin American scientists, despite the disease being endemic to our region. The present manuscript is the product of a community

of researchers who have worked directly with *Dalbulus maidis*, maize growers, and local institutions across Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, the United States of America, and now Canada. It is precisely this community-driven perspective that underpins our proposal to recognize ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma zea*’ as a distinct, ecologically and genomically defined species.

For these reasons, we cannot accept reviews that dismiss decades of field, taxonomic, and genomic work from Latin American and allied groups as if it were scientifically or politically peripheral. Scientific peer review must be rigorous, but it must also be respectful, free of insinuations about “non-ethical statements,” and attentive to the documented realities of pathogen biology, ecology, and genomics. In the detailed responses that follow, we show that our manuscript is fully consistent with both the IRPCM (2004) framework and its 2022 revision, and that the objections raised by the reviewers do not withstand a careful reading of either the guidelines or our data.

References (organized by years):

- Maramorosch K. The occurrence of two distinct types of corn stunt in Mexico. *Plant Dis Rep* 1955;39:896–898.
- Nault LR. Maize bushy stunt and corn stunt: a comparison of disease symptoms, pathogen host ranges, and vectors. *Phytopathology* 1980;70:659–662.
- Harrison, N. A., Richardson, P. A., Tsai, J. H., Ebbert, M. A. & Kramer, J. B. (1996a). PCR assay for detection of the phytoplasma associated with maize bushy stunt disease. *Plant Dis* 80, 263–269.
- Lee I-M, Gundersen-Rindal DE, Davis RE, Bottner KD, Marcone C et al. ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’, a novel phytoplasma taxon associated with aster yellows and related diseases. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;54:1037–1048.

Reviewers' comments:

Reviewer 1:

An annotated and commented version of the manuscript is provided for authors to better explain detailed points.

1. methodological rigor. The data presented are methodological good however using genomes mainly produced from insect vectors that are also vectoring other bacteria as in this case reduce the reliability of the molecular data that must be provided from a clean source only colonized by the pathogen studied and it is well known that insect also has larger microbiomes than plants. In this case the fact of **being vector of two bacteria further jeopardize the reliability of the molecular data.**

Response: We disagree with the reviewer. This comment is technically inaccurate, and it is a very outdated statement considering the progress and advances in genomics, sequencing technologies, and modern bioinformatic pipelines that now allow the confident assembly of contamination-free genomes. With the sequencing depth we achieved (from 44 to 282 million reads per sample), and the comprehensive bioinformatic steps we followed to recover and assemble the genomes (see Lines 185–191: “For genome reconstruction, raw reads were quality-trimmed using fastp v.0.23.4 [47]. Taxonomic classification was performed with Kraken2 v.2.1.3 [48] against the core-nt database. To eliminate host-derived reads (e.g., from leafhoppers, humans, and plants), we used KrakenTools v.1.2 (<https://github.com/jenniferlu717/KrakenTools>). Filtered reads were assembled using two

metagenomic assemblers, MEGAHIT v.1.1.4 [49] and MetaSPAdes v.4.1.0 [50], to evaluate assembler performance and enhance contig recovery.”), we were able to easily assemble high-quality genomes. Additionally, we did include samples from infected corn plants as one of the sources used to assemble the MBSP-BR genome (GenBank: SAMN50092827). These plants were a ‘clean source’, because they were infected by *Dalbulus maidis* in a dedicated colony used for research and infected by ‘*Ca. P. zea*’. Several high-impact studies clearly demonstrate that obtaining high-quality prokaryotic genomes from insects is **entirely feasible and unproblematic**. For instance:

- Medina Muñoz, M., Lysne, J. A., Foo, A., Brettell, L. E., Nichols, H. L., UWMadison Capstone in Microbiology Students, et al. (2024). *MosAIC: An annotated collection of mosquito-associated bacteria with high-quality genome assemblies*. **PLoS Biology**, 22(11), e3002897. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pbio.3002897>
 - Du, L. F., Shi, W., Cui, X. M., et al. (2025). *Genome-resolved metagenomics reveals microbiome diversity across 48 tick species*. **Nature Microbiology**, 10, 2631–2645. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-025-02119-z>
2. presentation of results. This is quite confusing in several parts, and some non necessary data are incorporated.

Response: Thank you for the comment. We will try to determine what the reviewer means by “non-necessary data,” based on the notes provided in the annotated PDF file.

We presented the results in the same manner as in our previous IJSEM publications from my group:

- Valdez-López, J. L., Palafox-Leal, N. L., Santos-Lopez, G., Fantino, E. I., Mohammadi, S., Levesque, R. C., Méndez-Lozano, J., Mora-Zamudio, C. I., Rodríguez-Negrete, E. A., Santos-Cervantes, M. E., **Pérez-López, E.**, & Leyva-López, N. E. (2026). *Pectobacterium sinaloense sp. nov., a novel phytopathogenic species isolated from potato plants in Mexico*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 76(2). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.007076>
- **Pérez-López, E.**, Omar, A. F., Al-Jamhan, K. M., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2018). *Molecular identification and characterization of the new 16SrIX-J and cpn60 UT IX-J phytoplasma subgroup associated with chicory bushy stunt disease in Saudi Arabia*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 68(2). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.002530>
- Omar, A. F., Aljmhan, K. A., Alsohim, A. S., & **Pérez-López, E.** (2018). *Potato purple top disease associated with the novel subgroup 16SrII-X phytoplasma*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 68(11). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.003033>
- **Pérez-López, E.**, Olivier, C. Y., Luna-Rodríguez, M., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2016). *Phytoplasma classification and phylogeny based on in silico and in vitro RFLP analysis of cpn60 universal target sequences*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 66(12). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.001501>
- **Pérez-López, E.**, Luna-Rodríguez, M., Olivier, C. Y., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2016). *The underestimated diversity of phytoplasmas in Latin America*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 66(1). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.000726>
- **Perez-Lopez, E.**, Vincent, C., Moreau, D., Hammond, C., Town, J., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2018). *A novel ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris’ subgroup 16SrI-(E/AI)AI associated with blueberry stunt*

disease in eastern Canada. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 69(2). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.003100>

- Pérez-López, E., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2016). *Detection and identification of the heterogeneous novel subgroup 16SrXIII-(A/I)I phytoplasma associated with strawberry green petal disease and Mexican periwinkle virescence*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 66(11). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.001365>
3. how the style and organization of the paper communicates and represents key findings. The manuscript organization provides too much information that are not strictly connected to the aim of the manuscript and also some of the sentences are in some manner contradictory.

Response: The IJSEM does not have a specific required format for the description of new bacterial species, and it is up to the authors to provide the necessary elements to demonstrate that the proposed taxon is indeed new. As we discuss later, it was essential to include all the details we provided because the main evidence supporting the delineation of ‘*Ca. P. zae*’ was Rule c of the IRPCM.

A clear example of an IJSEM phytoplasma species description that includes maps and information similar to ours is the delineation of ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma vignae*’ (Rodrigues Jardim et al., 2024). Furthermore, during the delineation of ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma tritici*’ through Rule c of the IRPCM, the authors provided the same type of evidence we present, regarding vector and host biology, even though they chose not to include additional figures (Zhao et al., 2021).

References:

- Rodrigues Jardim, B., et al. (2024). ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma vignae*’, assigning a species description to a long-known phytoplasma occurring in northern Australia. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 74, 006502. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.006502>
 - Zhao, Y., Wei, W., Davis, R. E., Lee, I.-M., & Bottner-Parker, K. D. (2021). *The agent associated with blue dwarf disease in wheat represents a new phytoplasma taxon, ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma tritici’*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 71, 004604. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.004604>
4. literature analysis or discussion. The literature is reported almost in full but not appropriately used for taxon delineation. The results presented clearly show that there is no new taxon while in the discussion what to demonstrate the contrary also with **some non ethical statements**.

Response: This comment appears intended to undermine the manuscript and steer the editor toward rejection, rather than being constructive or truthful. We have cited all the state-of-the-art literature in phytoplasma taxonomy and species delineation. Here are some examples:

- Lee IM, Gundersen-Rindal DE, Davis RE, Bartoszyk IM. Revised classification scheme of phytoplasmas based on RFLP analyses of 16S rRNA and ribosomal protein gene sequences. *Int J Syst Bacteriol* 1998;48:1153–1169.
- Lee IM, Gundersen-Rindal DE, Davis RE, Bottner KD, Marcone C et al. ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’, a novel phytoplasma taxon associated with aster yellows and related diseases. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;54:1037–1048.

- IRPCM. ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma’, a taxon for the wall-less, non-helical prokaryotes that colonize plant phloem and insects. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;54:1243–1255.
- Rodrigues Jardim B, Tran-Nguyen LTT, Gambley C, Webster C, Kehoe M et al. ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma vignae’, assigning a species description to a long-known phytoplasma occurring in northern Australia. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2024;74:006502.
- Davis RE, Harrison NA, Zhao Y, Wei W, Dally EL. ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma hispanicum’, a novel taxon associated with Mexican periwinkle virescence disease of *Catharanthus roseus*. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2016;66:3463–3467.
- Fernández FD, Galdeano E, Kornowski MV, Arneodo J, Conci LR. Description of ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma meliae’, a phytoplasma associated with Chinaberry yellowing in South America. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2016;66:5244–5251.
- Bertaccini A, Arocha-Rosete Y, Contaldo N, Duduk B, Fiore N et al. Revision of the ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma’ species description guidelines. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2022;72.
- Zhao Y, Wei W, Davis RE, Lee IM, Bottner-Parker KD. The agent associated with blue dwarf disease in wheat represents a new phytoplasma taxon, ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma tritici’. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2021;71:004604.
- Zhao Y, Davis RE. Criteria for phytoplasma 16Sr group/subgroup delineation and the need of a platform for proper registration of new groups and subgroups. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2016;66:2121–2123.

If the reviewer would like us to cite something specific, please let us know. Additionally, one statement is particularly problematic and a **character attack towards the authors** and requires immediate clarification: “with some non-ethical statements.” What do you mean by this?

Here the comments provided in the annotated file (165 comments or modifications):

1. The same manuscript is already available as preprint in bioRxiv since two months

Response: Yes, our work was posted as a preprint on bioRxiv (doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2025.08.28.671991>). This is a modern and widely accepted practice in the scientific community to prevent delays in the release of important data, avoid scooping, and ensure that the information is freely accessible, even when the final published article may not be open access due to high publication costs. As IJSEM does not have any specific guidelines prohibiting preprints, we did not violate any rule by doing so.

2. Change The Americas for The American Continent.

Response: We respectfully disagree with the reviewer. When referring to North America and South America as a whole, the appropriate term is “the Americas,” as supported by the Encyclopedia Britannica (<https://www.britannica.com/place/Americas>). We did not change anything in the revised manuscript.

3. Avoid using personalization.

Response: Here, the reviewer was referring to the use of “we sequenced.” This is not the first time a reviewer has suggested avoiding personalized language, but we consistently defend its use. Why?

Because science is not abstract, we performed the experiments, and we stand behind the work. The first-person voice is also clearer and more accessible for non-native English speakers, including the authors of this manuscript. We invite the reviewer to consult the two sources cited below, which address this topic in detail.

- **Brennan, E. B.** (2024). “I” versus “the author”: The power of first-person voice when writing about science. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 121(22), e2316966121. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2316966121>
 - **Nature Editorial.** (2016). Scientific language is becoming more informal. *Nature*, 539, 140. <https://www.nature.com/articles/539140a>
4. Change U.S. by **USA**. (This was edited over 10 times in the pdf file)

Response: Corrected as suggested through the manuscript. See Line 37, 38, 102, 143, and 181.

5. Reviewer suggested to write ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ instead of ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma asteris*’ in the abstract, line 40.

Response: The suggestion is not correct, but neither was the initial name we provided. Because this is the first time the species is mentioned, it should read ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’. This has now been corrected in the revised abstract, line 40. Thank you for pointing this out.

6. There is a question mark (?) marking this sentence in the abstract from Lines 43 to 45: “Comparative genomic analyses revealed unique gene clusters in ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ associated with amino acid transport, defense mechanisms, and protein turnover, which may contribute to its specialization in corn”.

Response: We don’t know what this means, so nothing was changed in the revised manuscript.

7. The reviewer writes ‘Above’

Response: Here the reviewer is referring to ‘near the established’ in Line 43 of the abstract.

The full phrase is from Line 41 to 43: “Average nucleotide identity (ANI) and average amino acid identity (AAI) values between ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ are 97.70–98.00% and 96.65–96.88%, respectively, both near the established species delineation thresholds.”. Although it is correct that the ANI value established in 2022 (Bertaccini et al. 2022) was 95%, there is no AAI threshold established yet, so technically the reviewer and our initial statement are not completely correct.

We corrected this as follows Line 41-43: “Genome-wide average nucleotide identity between ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and all available ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strains genomes was between 92.6% and 98.4%”.

8. Proof for this must be provided.

Response: The reviewer is referring to this phrase in Line 46-47: “supports its recognition as a novel species under Rule c of the IRPCM guidelines”

At this point of the revision, **we believe the reviewer has not yet read the manuscript**, as this is what we present there: the evidence supporting the designation of a new species, which is based primarily on Rule c of the IRPCM guidelines (IRPCM 2004), still valid despite the 2022 updates (Bertaccini et al. 2022). Now, what is Rule c? Below we copy the relevant section directly from the 2004 manuscript:

(c) There are, however, cases of phytoplasmas that share >97.5% (in 2022 changed to 98.65%) of their 16S rRNA gene sequence, but clearly represent ecologically separated populations and, therefore, may deserve description as separate species. For such cases, description of two different species is recommended only when all three of the following conditions apply:

- (i) the two phytoplasmas are transmitted by different vectors;
- (ii) the two phytoplasmas have a different natural plant host (or, at least, their behaviour is significantly different in the same plant host);
- (iii) there is evidence of significant molecular diversity, achieved by either hybridization to cloned DNA probes, serological reaction or PCR-based assay.

How does this apply to '*Ca. P. zea*'?

- (i) There have been established a great diversity of leafhoppers able to transmit '*Ca. P. asteris*'. However, only leafhoppers into the genus *Dalbulus*, are able to transmit '*Ca. P. zea*'. This was very detailed from Line 120-135:

"Dalbulus (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) is a Neotropical genus comprising eleven recognized species, all specialized in corn (*Z. mays*), related teosintes (*Zea* spp.), or *Tripsacum* spp. as host plants [26,27]. Among these, *D. maidis* (**Figure 1B**) and *D. elimatus* (Ball) are the most prominent, feeding on both maize and teosintes [26,27]. Other species such as *D. gelbus*, *D. longulus*, and *D. guevarai* are associated with maize and/or *Tripsacum* spp., whereas *D. quinquenotatus*, *D. guvnani*, *D. chiapensis*, *D. gramalotes*, *D. charlesi*, and *D. tripsacoides* are associated exclusively with *Tripsacum* spp. [27].

Although experimental studies have shown that other *Dalbulus* species and leafhoppers from different genera (e.g., *Graminella nigrifrons* Forbes) can acquire and transmit MBSP under controlled conditions, only *D. maidis*, commonly known as the corn leafhopper, and *D. elimatus*, known as the Mexican corn leafhopper, are confirmed natural vectors [10,28-30]. Recently in Brazil, the invasive planthopper *Leptodelphax maculigera* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae) was found to be simultaneously infected with MBSP, maize rayado fino virus and maize striate mosaic virus [31, 32]. However, further laboratory experiments indicated that this species is not a vector of the MBSP, and pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is its primary host, rather than maize [33]. These aspects highlight a high degree of vector specificity in the transmission ecology of MBSP."

- (ii) It is clearly established in the literature that '*Ca. P. zea*' specifically affects corn and other plants within the genus *Zea*. This was presented in the original manuscript from lines 110 to 118.

“Maize bushy stunt (MBS) was first detected on corn plants in Mexico over six decades ago [2]. The main symptoms of MBS include chlorotic striping on the leaves, foliar reddening and yellowing, stunted growth, lateral branching along the stalk, deformed or poorly filled ears, and a characteristic bushy appearance [22,23]. These symptoms are consistently observed in both commercial hybrids and native landraces of maize [7,10] (**Figure 1A**). Crop losses attributed to MBS phytoplasma infection can range from 35% to as high as 93%, depending largely on the prevalence of the insect vectors and timing of the infection [24,25]. Although other members of the genus *Zea* have been shown experimentally to be susceptible to MBS phytoplasma, *Z. mays* remains the only confirmed natural host [10].”

Figure 1. Unique host, vector and geographic distribution of Maize Bushy Stunt phytoplasma **A**) Maize plant showing typical symptoms of Maize Bushy Stunt disease, including leaf reddening and yellowing, and stunting, observed in a field in central and south Brazil. **B**) Geographic distribution of *Dalbulus maidis* (yellow), *D. elimatus* (green), and confirmed reports of Maize Bushy Stunt Phytoplasma (red) across the Americas. The inset image shows an adult *D. maidis* specimen (scale bar = 1 mm), the primary insect vector associated with MBSP transmission.

- (iii) Yes, there is significant evidence that ‘*Ca. P. zae*’ is molecularly divergent enough from previously delineated ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species as presented in the revised manuscript from Line 232 to 264:

“Pairwise identity analysis of 16S rRNA genes revealed > 99.8% identity between MBSP and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’, but <98.65% identity with other described ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species. While MBSP and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ share specific diagnostic regions within the 16S rRNA gene [9], **unique nucleotide sequences** were observed in ‘*Ca. P. zae*’-related strains (**Table 1**). Eleven polymorphic sites differentiated ‘*Ca. P. zae*’ from ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’, notably at positions 1319–1321, 1367–1369, and 151–153 (**Table 1**). The 16S

rRNA gene showed >99% identity between '*Ca. P. zae*' and '*Ca. P. asteris*', but lower identity with '*Ca. P. tritici*' (98.82%) and '*Ca. P. lycopersici*' (96.71%). Given the subtle differences and high 16S similarity (threshold for species delineation has been set at >98.65%), we examined additional conserved genes for improved resolution.

Among the protein-coding genes analyzed, *rpoB* and *rps3* provided the best discriminatory power (**Table 1**). Nucleotide identity values for '*Ca. P. zae*' vs. '*Ca. P. asteris*' were 99.31% (*rpoB*) and 99.34% (*rps3*), while identity dropped to 95.93% and 96.17%, respectively, when compared to '*Ca. P. tritici*'. The *rpoB* gene contained five distinct nucleotide differences (e.g., at positions 1268–1270 and 2850–2852), while *rps3* presented six (e.g., 17–19 and 570–572) (**Table 1**). Although *rpoB* is not part of the IRPCM-recognized set for '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' classification, it has been successfully used to distinguish closely related '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains [42,61]. The analysis of the *cpn60OUT* revealed three SNPs at positions 61, 394, and 1075, supporting its continued relevance in phylogenetic classification schemes, even though we did not detect the polymorphism at position 125 previously reported for MBS-Ver [62]. The *secY* and *secA* genes also demonstrated high identity (99.4% and 99.3%, respectively, vs. '*Ca. P. asteris*') but showed lower similarity with '*Ca. P. tritici*' (~95.9%), each with nine informative differences.

Pangenome analysis reinforced these findings. Among 3,720 identified gene clusters (GCs), 276 were shared across all strains (core GCs), while 45 accessory GCs were exclusive to '*Ca. P. zae*'. Among the accessory gene clusters, we identified genes associated with amino acid transport and metabolism (15 genes), defense mechanisms (8 genes), and posttranslational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones (2 genes). A substantial fraction (137 genes) lacked functional annotation (**Table S5**). The pangenome clustering based on shared gene clusters content aligned with the phylogenetic patterns, with '*Ca. P. zae*' grouping alongside '*Ca. P. asteris*' and '*Ca. P. tritici*' (**Figure 5A**). ANI analyses confirmed this relationship, showing 92.6–98.4% identity between '*Ca. P. zae*' and all available genomes for '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains, and 93.3–93.4% between '*Ca. P. zae*' and '*Ca. P. tritici*' (**Figure 5B-C, Table S6, Figure S1**). AAI analyses revealed a similar pattern: '*Ca. P. zae*' and '*Ca. P. asteris*' shared high similarity, with AAI values ranging from 96.65% to 96.88%, whereas '*Ca. P. tritici*' exhibited lower values, between 91.62% and 91.90% (**Table S7**)."

The newly updated criteria do not totally override previously established criteria. As stated clearly in Bertaccini et al. (2022): "The revised guidelines support all the previously assigned '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species, except four that must be adjusted to fit the revised guidelines. Previous International Research Programme on Comparative Mycoplasmaology guidelines [1] should be followed if relevant for a complete description of the new '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species when not conflicting with the present revised guidelines."

[1] IRPCM. *Candidatus* Phytoplasma, a taxon for the wall-less, non-helical prokaryotes that colonise plant phloem and insects. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004; 54:1243–1255.

The key part of this extract is "**when not conflicting with the present revised guidelines**". Based on the way we presented our results and conducted the analyses, it may initially appear that our delineation conflicts with the revised thresholds:

"The new thresholds include a 16S rRNA gene sequence identity of 98.65 %, a genome ANI of 95 %, and two among five suggested housekeeping genes. For example, if the 16S rRNA gene sequence identity for a given phytoplasma is <98.65 %, there is no need to check other sequences. If the 16S rRNA gene sequence identity is >98.65 % and the genome ANI is <95 %, checking other genes is not required.

Housekeeping genes should be used when 16S rRNA gene sequence identities are >98.65 % and the whole genome sequence is unavailable.”

We initially compared ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ genomes strictly with the ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ reference genome (GCA_038505995.1), obtaining an ANI of 97.7–98.0%. However, we have now expanded the analysis and compared ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ genomes with all 20 available ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strain genomes in NCBI (Genbank accession numbers: GCA_038505995.1 (Ref), GCA_038396745.1, GCA_047530585.1, GCA_030686925.1, GCF_019396865.1, GCA_000012225.1, GCA_020714625.1, GCA_004214875.1, GCA_041920595.1, GCA_047530585.1, GCA_036985145.1, GCA_001866375.1, GCA_018283495.1, GCA_002554195.1, GCA_000744065.1, GCA_000803325.1, GCA_000009845.1, GCA_013372025.1, GCA_003181115.1, GCA_005093185.1), finding **<95% genome-wide ANI identity** relative to 4 of the ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ strains (See new revised **Table S6** and the new **Figure S1**).

The four ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ genomes presenting **<95% genome-wide ANI identity** relative to ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ have been clearly validated as 16Srl and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strains. Additionally, the quality of the sequences is optimal with several of them assembled in the last 5 years, as the references below can confirm:

References:

- Toth, R., Ilic, A.-M., Huettel, B., Duduk, B., & Kube, M. 2024. Divergence within the taxon ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’ confirmed by comparative genome analysis of carrot strains. *Microorganisms*, 12, 1016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms12051016>
- Bai, X., Correa, V. R., Toruño, T. Y., Ammar, E.-D., Kamoun, S., & Hogenhout, S. A. 2009. AY-WB phytoplasma secretes a protein that targets plant cell nuclei. *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions*, 22(1), 18–30. <https://doi.org/10.1094/MPMI-22-1-0018>
- Sparks, M. E., Bottner-Parker, K. D., Gundersen-Rindal, D. E., & Lee, I.-M. 2018. Draft genome sequence of the New Jersey aster yellows strain of ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*’. *PLoS ONE*, 13(2), e0192379. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192379>
- Song, S., Wang, Q., Huo, L., Xie, L., Chen, J., Cui, H., Dai, Z., Kang, J., Li, Y., Guo, W., Chen, J., Kang, L., & Zhang, X. 2025. The phytoplasma (‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma arecae*’) is the crucial pathogen causing areca palm yellow leaf disease. *Science Bulletin*, 70(6), 847–851. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2024.10.020>

Is this in compliance with the 2022 guidelines? Yes. This is exactly the same situation under which ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ was accepted as a new species according to the revised guidelines.

During the delineation of ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ Zhao et al. (2021) stated: “As shown in Table 2, the ANI scores between the WBD phytoplasma and diverse ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ strains varied from 93.88–94.69 %, justifying the WBD phytoplasma as a new taxon separate from ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’. Taken together, these results indicate that ecological uniqueness of the WBD phytoplasma has its roots in the genome.” This might be true for the 10 strains presented in the manuscript, but we don’t know if it is the case for all the 20 genomes available.

Bertaccini et al. (2022) echoed this language during the updates of the rules regarding ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’: **“The proposal of this new taxon was based on its unique vectorship, a distinctive symptomatology in**

its predominant plant host, and <95% genome-wide ANI identity compared to several '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains."

9. this is not a scientific reason other could propose names only for the same reasons but not supported scientifically as it is the case for this

Response: The reviewer is referring to the following sentence in the abstract: "The designation '*Candidatus* *Phytoplasma zae*' is therefore proposed by members of the research community who have studied this pathogen for over a decade."

As demonstrated in point 8 of the annotated PDF file, the delineation of this new species is fully supported by scientific evidence. The reviewer's claim appears to stem from not having read the manuscript carefully. We are not removing the statement because it highlights a fundamental point: **why do we delineate new taxa in the first place, and what is the semantic, scientific, and societal value of doing so?**

The designation of '*Ca. P. zae*' is not arbitrary, nor is it based solely on tradition or preference. It reflects over a decade of research carried out by multiple independent groups, and it represents an essential step in standardizing the communication and understanding of this pathogen. Clear taxonomic naming is crucial because phytoplasmas are highly diverse, and their biological behavior, host range, epidemiology, and management implications differ substantially across groups.

From an applied perspective, **establishing an accurate and stable taxonomic identity directly benefits growers, agronomists, diagnostic laboratories, and plant-health authorities.** A well-defined species name allows us to:

- communicate the disease and its causal agent with clarity and consistency,
- develop diagnostic tools that specifically target this taxon,
- design surveillance programs focused on the correct pathogen,
- compare disease outbreaks across regions without semantic ambiguity,
- generate extension material for producers that is understandable and actionable,
- consolidate scientific knowledge under a single, unambiguous nomenclatural entity.

Without a formal and scientifically justified designation, the communication around this pathogen becomes confusing, especially for non-specialists. Producers, regulatory agencies, and even students or early-career scientists may struggle to differentiate this phytoplasma from others that are genetically similar but biologically distinct. Naming the species properly **reduces confusion, improves disease reporting, and facilitates the development of targeted management strategies.**

Therefore, the sentence in the abstract is not casual, it reflects the historical, scientific, and practical trajectory of research on this pathogen. Taxonomic clarity is not only a scientific responsibility; it directly impacts disease management and knowledge translation. For these reasons, and because the delineation is firmly supported by the IRPCM rules and by our genomic, ecological, and biological evidence, **we will retain this statement in the manuscript.**

References about the importance of taxonomy in plant pathology and society:

- Glawe D.A. (2002). Much more than phylogenies: A utilitarian view of the taxonomy of plant pathogenic fungi. DOI: 10.1094/APSnetFeature-2002-0902.

- Pritchard L, Brown CT, Harrington B, Heath LS, Pierce-Ward NT & Vinatzer BA. (2022). Could a focus on the “why” of taxonomy help taxonomy better respond to the needs of science and society? *Front. Microbiol.* 13:887310. doi:10.3389/fmicb.2022.887310.
10. deposition of alive strains of the phytoplasma then should also be provided or no??? inconsistency of data

Response: The reviewer is referring to this from the data availability statement: “*Dalbulus maidis* specimens from Brazil, Oklahoma, and Iowa, suspected positive for MBSP from the same molecularly explored batch were deposited in the Canadian National Collection of Insects, Arachnids, and Nematodes under voucher numbers CNC2183353-CNC2183354 (Brazil), CNC2183355-CNC2183356 (Oklahoma), CNC2183357-CNC2183358 (Iowa). Dr. Joel Kits (joel.kits@agr.gc.ca) is the curator responsible for the Hemiptera collection. *D. maidis* specimens positive for MBS from Brazil were also deposited in SisGen (<https://sisgen.gov.br>) under voucher number A308CA9.”

Either this is a very ill-intentioned comment, or the reviewer is unaware that phytoplasmas are unculturable and therefore cannot be deposited in prokaryote culture collections. Although there is a small collection of phytoplasma-infected plants in Italy (<https://www.ipwgnat.org/collection>), depositing material in this collection is not required. For this reason, we deposited phytoplasma-infected insects in recognized collections in Canada and Brazil.

The only phytoplasma species delineation manuscript published in IJSEM that mentions depositing material in any collection is the delineation of ‘*Ca. P. vignae*’. All other phytoplasma species descriptions provide only sequence-deposit information. In that paper, the material deposited was: “Preserved plant material of samples BAWM-245 and BAWM-336 were submitted to the Victorian Plant Pathology Herbarium (VPRI) under the accessions VPRI 44368 and VPRI 44369, respectively.”

11. The reviewer seems to hate the acronym MBSP (it was crossed out). The reviewer pointed this throughout the manuscript.

Response: This is a widely accepted acronym for this phytoplasma. We defined it in Line 70: “**MBS phytoplasma (MBSP)**”. We kept it throughout the manuscript.

12. add Latin name of these varieties for clarity

Response: The reviewer is referring to “and more recently in Mexico in association with native maize varieties”. Varieties are a taxonomic rank between species and subspecies, so the latin name would be (*Zea mays* L.). Nothing to correct.

13. the 'Candidatus' genus in general was proposed before and not for these bacteria please revise appropriately, the phytoplasma was added in 2004 while the use of 'Candidatus' as provisional taxon was proposed in 1995. The literature is correct but the text is very confusing

Response: The reviewer is referring to “Due to their extreme difficulty in being cultured in axenic media, phytoplasmas lack measurable phenotypic characteristics for classical taxonomic classification. The International Committee of Systematic Bacteriology Subcommittee for the Taxonomy of Mollicutes,

together with the International Research Program for Comparative Mycoplasmaology (IRPCM), addressed this by establishing taxonomic conventions for uncultured bacteria [11] and creating the provisional genus 'Candidatus Phytoplasma' [12]."

References:

[11] Murray RGE, Stackebrandt E. Taxonomic note: Implementation of the provisional status Candidatus for incompletely described procaryotes. *Int J Syst Bacteriol* 1995;45:186–187.

[12] IRPCM. 'Candidatus Phytoplasma', a taxon for the wall-less, non-helical prokaryotes that colonize plant phloem and insects. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;54:1243–1255.

The text was changed to improve clarity from Line 79 to 84: "Because phytoplasmas cannot be cultured in axenic media, they lack the measurable phenotypic characteristics required for classical taxonomic classification. For this reason, the taxonomic conventions for unculturable bacteria established by the International Committee of Systematic Bacteriology Subcommittee for the Taxonomy of Mollicutes, together with the International Research Program for Comparative Mycoplasmaology (IRPCM), are currently followed [11], providing the framework under which the provisional genus 'Ca. Phytoplasma' was created [12]."

14. 'Candidatus Phytoplasma' for 'Ca. Phytoplasma'

Response: Changed as suggested in line 83.

15. these guideline were officially revised and revision was published three year ago, this was neglected here those definition must be updated since the revision was officially approved by the community

Response: Reviewer is referring to: "According to IRPCM guidelines [13], three principal criteria are used to define new 'Ca. Phytoplasma' taxa: (1) a unique 16S rRNA gene sequence (≥ 1200 bp) defining the reference strain, with closely related strains distinguished by minor sequence differences; (2) less than 97.5% sequence identity with the 16S rRNA gene of any described species, or (3) if above this threshold, evidence that the organism represents an ecologically distinct population ("Rule c"), demonstrated by differences in insect vectors, plant hosts, and supporting molecular divergence. Recent revisions to these delineation criteria also incorporate analyses of additional housekeeping genes and whole-genome average nucleotide identity (ANI), adopting the general bacterial species boundary of >95 – 96% ANI [17,19, 20]."

As we stated: "Recent revisions to these delineation criteria also incorporate analyses of additional housekeeping genes and whole-genome average nucleotide identity (ANI), adopting the general bacterial species boundary of >95 – 96% ANI [17,19, 20]." We also corrected the value in point two according to the 22 revised criteria as follow in Line 88: "(2) less or equal 98.65%".

References

[17] Bertaccini A, Arocha-Rosete Y, Contaldo N, Duduk B, Fiore N et al. Revision of the 'Candidatus Phytoplasma' species description guidelines. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2022;72.

[19] Yarza P, Yilmaz P, Pruesse E, Glöckner FO, Ludwig W et al. Uniting the classification of cultured and uncultured bacteria and archaea using 16S rRNA gene sequences. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 2014;12:635–645.

[20] Kim M, Oh HS, Park SC, Chun J. Towards a taxonomic coherence between average nucleotide identity and 16S rRNA gene sequence similarity for species demarcation of prokaryotes. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2014;64:346–351.

So, nothing else to change in the text.

16. Triticii by tritici

Response: Changed as suggested throughout the manuscript.

17. Of America

Response: Corrected as suggested in Line 97 and 100: United States of America.

18. incorrect sentence since phytoplasmas are not defined as causing diseases for the lack of koch postulates fulfillment

Response: Reviewer referring to: “These detections, represent the first confirmed reports of MBSP likely causing MBS in these USA states.”

We only must change the word “causing” to, “associated”, and we would be respecting the consensus by the phytoplasma community. That’s what we did from Line 101-102: “These detections, represent the first confirmed reports of MBSP associated to MBS in these USA states.”

19. 16Srl-B phytoplasmas were detected in corn in many other places in America and also in Europe and in Asia and authors do no report these findings here.

Response: It is difficult to determine which specific statement in the manuscript this comment refers to. When we peer-review a manuscript and make a claim of this nature, we also provide the corresponding references. We never stated that corn cannot be affected by other phytoplasmas; however, MBSP has only been reported in the Americas, and we provided the pertinent information supporting this.

20. one Continent do not represent geographic restriction, before the geographic restriction considered where only Country, also South America cannot be considered a geographic restriction since many countries there

Response: On what basis did the reviewer make this statement? Rule c clearly states: “(c) There are, however, cases of phytoplasmas that share >97.5% of their 16S rRNA gene sequence, but clearly represent ecologically separated populations...”. As you can see, there is no specificity regarding regional scale. Countries are sociopolitical constructions, not ecological concepts.

21. same symptoms are reported in Europe associated with this and other phytoplasmas.

Response: This statement is not accurate and is reductionist. The disease affecting corn in Serbia is called Maize Redness (Duduk and Bertaccini, 2007), and the only symptom it shares with Maize Bushy

Stunt is the red coloration of the leaves, and maybe some corncob malformations, symptoms that appears very late in MBS infections. The symptoms of Maize Redness are: “besides redness, affected plants show early and abnormal ripening, dry precociously, and have poor, shriveled grains,” which differ substantially from the MBS symptoms described in Lines 111–114: “The main symptoms of MBS include chlorotic striping on the leaves, foliar reddening and yellowing, stunted growth, lateral branching along the stalk, deformed or poorly filled ears, and a characteristic bushy appearance.” (See symptoms below). The vector of Maize Redness was identified as *Reptalus panzeri* (Jović et al., 2009), more evidence that are clearly two different pathosystems. See the symptoms in point 8.

References:

- Jović, J., Cvrković, T., Mitrović, M., Krnjajić, S., Petrović, A., Redinbaugh, M. G., Pratt, R. C., Hogenhout, S. A., & Toševski, I. (2009). Stolbur phytoplasma transmission to maize by *Reptalus panzeri* and the disease cycle of Maize Redness in Serbia. *Phytopathology*, 99(9), 1053–1061. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PHYTO-99-9-1053>
- Duduk, B., & Bertaccini, A. (2007). Corn with symptoms of reddening: New host of stolbur phytoplasma. *Plant Disease*, 90(10), 1313–1313. <https://doi.org/10.1094/PD-90-1313>

22. not pertinent to the topic of this manuscript not relevant for the proposal of the taxon

Response: The reviewer is referring to Line 115 to 118: “Crop losses attributed to MBS phytoplasma infection can range from 35% to as high as 93%, depending largely on the prevalence of the insect vectors and timing of the infection [24,25]. Although other members of the genus *Zea* have been shown experimentally to be susceptible to MBS phytoplasma, *Z. mays* remains the only confirmed natural host [10].”

We don’t see why not, and we have seen similar information in other manuscript describing phytoplasma species. For example:

‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma wodyetiae*’ (Naderali et al. 2017): Diverse plant species in the family Arecaceae, commonly known as palms, have enormous appeal due to their high economic and aesthetic values. In the vast tropical and subtropical areas around the globe, palms provide unparalleled elegance and architectural stature in landscapes; their fruits, seeds, fronds (leaves) and stems are rich sources of food, biofuels, cosmetic products and timber [1].

‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma graminis*’ (Arocha et al. 2005): Sugarcane (*Saccharum officinarum* L.) is the most economically important crop in Cuba, where the control of pests and diseases is constrained by low-input farming systems, whereas papaya (*Carica papaya* L.) has been identified for development as an export crop with an estimated production of 55 000–60 000 tonnes per year. Yellow leaf syndrome (YLS) is one of five main diseases affecting Cuban sugarcane production (Peralta et al., 1999) and is associated with phytoplasmas (Arocha et al., 1999).

‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma tritici*’ (Zhao et al. 2021): Wheat blue dwarf (WBD) disease is a major limiting factor in winter wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) production in arid and semiarid areas of northwestern PR China. Although the WBD disease had long been present in the areas, especially in Shaanxi, Ningxia and Gansu provinces, scientific studies did not start until the early 1960s [1]. In the ensuing four decades,

outbreaks of the disease occurred more than a dozen times in Shaanxi province alone, inflicting economic losses and food shortage [2, 3].

References:

- Naderali, N., Nejat, N., Vadamalai, G., Davis, R. E., Wei, W., Harrison, N. A., Kong, L., Kadir, J., Tan, Y.-H., & Zhao, Y. (2017). 'Candidatus Phytoplasma wodyetiae', a new taxon associated with yellow decline disease of foxtail palm (*Wodyetia bifurcata*) in Malaysia. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 67, 3765–3772. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.002187>
- Arocha, Y., López, M., Piñol, B., Fernández, M., Picornell, B., Almeida, R., Palenzuela, I., Wilson, M. R., & Jones, P. (2005). 'Candidatus Phytoplasma graminis' and 'Candidatus Phytoplasma caricae', two novel phytoplasmas associated with diseases of sugarcane, weeds and papaya in Cuba. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 55, 2451–2463. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijse.0.63797-0>
- Zhao, Y., Wei, W., Davis, R. E., Lee, I.-M., & Bottner-Parker, K. D. (2021). *The agent associated with blue dwarf disease in wheat represents a new phytoplasma taxon, 'Candidatus Phytoplasma tritici'*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 71, 004604. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.004604>

23. this insect is also vectoring other bacteria that are infecting cont so this biological property is not exclusive transmission and weaken the proposal

Response: The reviewer is referring to Line 123 to 126 “*Dalbulus* (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) is a Neotropical genus comprising eleven recognized species, all specialized in corn (*Z. mays*), related teosintes (*Zea* spp.), or *Tripsacum* spp. as host plants [26,27]. Among these, *D. maidis* (**Figure 1B**) and *D. elimatus* (Ball) are the most prominent, feeding on both maize and teosintes [26,27].”

Yes, *Dalbulus maidis* is also a vector of *Spiroplasma kunkelii* (Mycoplasmatales: Spiroplasmataceae) and several viruses, including maize rayado fino virus, maize stripe virus, and maize dwarf mosaic virus. The association between *D. maidis* and the corn stunt disease complex (often referred to as Spiroplasma–virus complexes) has been extensively studied (Mendes 1938, Bradfute et al. 1981; Nault et al. 1984; Summers et al. 2004; Moya-Raigoza et al. 2007; Carloni et al. 2013; Torres-Moreno et al. 2015, Oliveira et al. 2022).

However, in more than eight decades of research on this leafhopper, there is **no evidence** that the presence of one pathogen affects the transmission of another pathogen. So, no, **this doesn't weaken the proposal**.

References:

- Mendes LOT. 1938. Observações sobre alguns insetos coletados sobre algodoeiro durante os anos de 1936 e 1937. Bol Tec Inst Agron 45:1–15
- Nault, L. R., Madden, L. V., Styer, W. E., Triplehorn, B. W., Shambaugh, G. F., and Heady, S. E. 1984. Pathogenicity of corn stunt spiroplasma and maize bushy stunt mycoplasma to their vector, *Dalbulus longulus*. *Phytopathology* 74: 977-979.
- Bradfute, O. E., Tsai, J. H., and Gordon, D. T. 1981. Corn stunt spiroplasma and viruses associated with a maize disease epidemic in southern Florida. *Plant Disease* 65:837-841.

- Oliveira, C.M., Frizzas, M.R. 2022. Eight Decades of *Dalbulus maidis* (DeLong & Wolcott) (Hemiptera, Cicadellidae) in Brazil: What We Know and What We Need to Know. *Neotrop Entomol* 51, 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13744-021-00932-9>
- Torres-Moreno, R., Moya-Raygoza, G., & Pérez-López, E. 2015. Absence of corn stunt Spiroplasma and maize bushy stunt phytoplasma in leafhoppers (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) that inhabit edge grasses throughout winter in Jalisco, Mexico. *Florida Entomologist*, 98(3),
- Carloni, E., Carpane, P., Paradell, S., Laguna, I., & Giménez Pecci, M. P. 2013. Presence of *Dalbulus maidis* (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) and of *Spiroplasma kunkelii* in the temperate region of Argentina. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 106(4), 1574–1581. <https://doi.org/10.1603/EC12323>
- Moya-Raygoza, G., Palomera-Avalos, V., & Galaviz-Mejía, C. 2007. Field overwintering biology of *Spiroplasma kunkelii* (Mycoplasmatales: Spiroplasmataceae) and its vector *Dalbulus maidis* (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae). *Annals of Applied Biology*, 151(2), 165–172. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1744-7348.2007.00185.x>
- Summers, C. G., Newton, A. S., Jr., & Opgenorth, D. C. 2004. Overwintering of corn leafhopper, *Dalbulus maidis* (Homoptera: Cicadellidae), and *Spiroplasma kunkelii* (Mycoplasmatales: Spiroplasmataceae) in California’s San Joaquin Valley. *Environmental Entomology*, 33(6), 1644–1651. <https://doi.org/10.1603/0046-225X-33.6.1644>

24. again weak point for taxon support (**I copied this directly from the pdf**)

Response: The reviewer is referring to Line 127 to 130 “Although experimental studies have shown that other *Dalbulus* species and leafhoppers from different genera (e.g., *Graminella nigrifrons* Forbes) can acquire and transmit MBSP under controlled conditions, only *D. maidis*, commonly known as the corn leafhopper, and *D. elimatus*, known as the Mexican corn leafhopper, are confirmed natural vectors [10,28-30].”

On the contrary, this provides even stronger evidence for the close evolutionary relationship between *D. maidis*, *D. elimatus*, and ‘*Ca. P. zae*’. *D. maidis* is arguably one of the most extensively studied leafhoppers in the world, and the fact that from 1938, when the first virus-like disease symptoms transmitted by the corn leafhopper were identified in Brazil, until 2026 there has been **no evidence whatsoever that any other leafhopper species can transmit this pathogen** is, in my view, a strong point, not a weak one.

Of course, this is a classic case of seeing the glass half full or half empty. If the reviewer has approached the manuscript from the beginning with a **negative and non-constructive lens**, then any point, regardless of its strength, can be framed negatively.

25. this is one of the reasons why in the update guideline this rule c is not accepted and only demonstration of new taxon

Response: The reviewer is referring to lines 132 to 133: “Recently in Brazil, the invasive planthopper *Leptodelphax maculigera* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae) was found to be simultaneously infected with MBSP, maize rayado fino virus and maize striate mosaic virus [31, 32].”

If the reviewer had continued reading, they would have seen lines 132 to 135: “However, further laboratory experiments indicated that this species is not a vector of the MBSP, and pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is its primary host, rather than maize [33]. These aspects highlight a high degree of vector specificity in the transmission ecology of MBSP.” As mentioned in point 24, this reinforces the specialization of the *Dalbulus*–corn–‘*Ca. P. zea*’ relationship.

IMPORTANT: The newly updated criteria do not totally override previously established criteria. As stated clearly in Bertaccini et al. (2022): “The revised guidelines support all the previously assigned ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species, except four that must be adjusted to fit the revised guidelines. Previous International Research Programme on Comparative Mycoplasmaology guidelines [1] should be followed if relevant for a complete description of the new ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species when not conflicting with the present revised guidelines.”

[1] IRPCM. *Candidatus* Phytoplasma, a taxon for the wall-less, non-helical prokaryotes that colonise plant phloem and insects. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004; 54:1243–1255.

The key part of this extract is “**when not conflicting with the present revised guidelines**”. Based on the way we presented our results and conducted the analyses, it may initially appear that our delineation conflicts with the revised thresholds:

“The new thresholds include a 16S rRNA gene sequence identity of 98.65 %, a genome ANI of 95 %, and two among five suggested housekeeping genes. For example, if the 16S rRNA gene sequence identity for a given phytoplasma is <98.65 %, there is no need to check other sequences. If the 16S rRNA gene sequence identity is >98.65 % and the genome ANI is <95 %, checking other genes is not required. Housekeeping genes should be used when 16S rRNA gene sequence identities are >98.65 % and the whole genome sequence is unavailable.”

This is because we initially compared ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ genomes strictly with the ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ reference genome (GCA_038505995.1), obtaining an ANI of 97.7–98.0%. However, we have now expanded the analysis and compared ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ genomes with all 20 available ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strain genomes in NCBI (Genbank accession numbers: GCA_038505995.1 (Ref), GCA_038396745.1, GCA_047530585.1, GCA_030686925.1, GCF_019396865.1, GCA_000012225.1, GCA_020714625.1, GCA_004214875.1, GCA_041920595.1, GCA_047530585.1, GCA_036985145.1, GCA_001866375.1, GCA_018283495.1, GCA_002554195.1, GCA_000744065.1, GCA_000803325.1, GCA_000009845.1, GCA_013372025.1, GCA_003181115.1, GCA_005093185.1), finding **<95% genome-wide ANI identity** relative to 4 of the ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ strains (See new revised **Table S6** and the new **Figure S1**).

Figure S1. Genome-wide average nucleotide identity matrix between the three '*Ca. P. zae*' genomes generated in this study and all available '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains genomes available in NCBI. In all cases the values are rounded up, final values are presented in **Table S6**.

The four '*Ca. P. asteris*' genomes presenting **<95% genome-wide ANI identity** relative to '*Ca. P. zae*' have been clearly validated as 16Srl and '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains. Additionally, the quality of the sequences is optimal with several of them assembled in the last 5 years, as the references below can confirm:

References:

- Toth, R., Ilic, A.-M., Huettel, B., Duduk, B., & Kube, M. 2024. Divergence within the taxon '*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*' confirmed by comparative genome analysis of carrot strains. *Microorganisms*, 12, 1016. <https://doi.org/10.3390/microorganisms12051016>
- Bai, X., Correa, V. R., Toruño, T. Y., Ammar, E.-D., Kamoun, S., & Hogenhout, S. A. 2009. AY-WB phytoplasma secretes a protein that targets plant cell nuclei. *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions*, 22(1), 18–30. <https://doi.org/10.1094/MPMI-22-1-0018>
- Sparks, M. E., Bottner-Parker, K. D., Gundersen-Rindal, D. E., & Lee, I.-M. 2018. Draft genome sequence of the New Jersey aster yellows strain of '*Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris*'. *PLoS ONE*, 13(2), e0192379. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0192379>
- Song, S., Wang, Q., Huo, L., Xie, L., Chen, J., Cui, H., Dai, Z., Kang, J., Li, Y., Guo, W., Chen, J., Kang, L., & Zhang, X. 2025. The phytoplasma ('*Candidatus Phytoplasma arecae*') is the crucial pathogen

causing areca palm yellow leaf disease. Science Bulletin, 70(6), 847–851.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2024.10.020>

Is this in compliance with the 2022 guidelines? Yes. This is exactly the same situation under which '*Ca. P. tritici*' was accepted as a new species according to the revised guidelines.

During the delineation of '*Ca. P. tritici*' Zhao et al. (2021) stated: "As shown in Table 2, the ANI scores between the WBD phytoplasma and diverse '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains varied from 93.88–94.69 %, justifying the WBD phytoplasma as a new taxon separate from '*Ca. P. asteris*'. Taken together, these results indicate that ecological uniqueness of the WBD phytoplasma has its roots in the genome." This might be true for the 10 strains presented in the manuscript, but we don't know if it is the case for all the 20 genomes available.

Bertaccini et al. (2022) echoed this language during the updates of the rules regarding '*Ca. P. tritici*': "**The proposal of this new taxon was based on its unique vectorship, a distinctive symptomatology in its predominant plant host, and <95% genome-wide ANI identity compared to several '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains.**"

But what has happened with the '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species delineated after the 2022 guidelines updates? Only one new taxon has been described since, and it is:

'*Candidatus Phytoplasma vignae*' (Rodrigues Gardim et al. 2024): This species was delineated based on 16S rRNA sequence similarity, exhibiting the highest similarity to '*Candidatus Phytoplasma omanense*' (98.03–98.10%) and '*Candidatus Phytoplasma phoenicium*' (96.87–97.20%), respectively. These identities are lower than the 98.65% threshold established by Bertaccini et al. (2022). **However**, we were curious as to why genome-wide ANI identity was not reported between '*Ca. P. vignae*' (JAUZLI0000000000, provided in the manuscript as the reference but not recognized in NCBI) and '*Ca. P. phoenicium*' (GCA_001189415.1). ('*Ca. P. omanense*' genome is not available.).

To clarify our new results, the revised manuscript was updated in Lines 41 to 43: "**Genome-wide average nucleotide identity between '*Ca. P. zae*' and all available '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains genomes was between 92.6% and 98.4%.**"

Lines 259 to 262: "ANI analyses confirmed this relationship, showing **92.6–98.4%** identity between '*Ca. P. zae*' and **all available genomes for '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains**, and 93.3–93.4% between '*Ca. P. zae*' and '*Ca. P. tritici*' (**Figure 5B-C, Table S6, Figure S1**)."

Lines 265 to 268: "Despite the relatively limited sequence divergence among these taxa, **ANI values <95% with multiple '*Ca. P. asteris*'-related strains**, the distinct ecological traits of '*Ca. P. zae*', including its specific insect vector, narrow host range, and geographically restricted distribution, provide strong support for its recognition as a separate species [12,17]."

Lines 276 to 280: Based on the unique host (*Z. mays*), unique vectors (*D. maidis* and *D. elimatus*), the geographic distribution restricted to the Americas, differentiating MBS phytoplasma from other '*Ca. P. asteris*'- related strains ecologically, **genome-wide average nucleotide identity values**, and the consensus from the community represented by the authors, we propose the designation of the novel '*Candidatus Phytoplasma zae*' species described as detailed below:

26. Very confusing

Response: The reviewer is referring to this phrase from Line 132-134: “However, further laboratory experiments indicated that this species is not a vector of the MBSP, and pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is its primary host, rather than maize [33].” We don’t see why this phrase is very confusing.

We change from Line 135 to 136: “and **that is** pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) its primary host”, to help reviewer understanding.

27. their insect vectors

Response: The reviewer is referring to the subtitle in Line 137: “GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OF MBSP AND ITS VECTORS”. We respectfully disagree because MBSP would be a singular entity in this specific scenario. No changes made in the revised manuscript.

28. Line 145, reviewer scratched out ‘our group’.

Response: Thank you for the suggestion, but we kept the original text.

29. ‘Most’ was scratched out in Line 149.

Response: Thank you for the suggestion, but we kept the original text.

30. what this means? please clarify

Response: The reviewer is referring to Line 150: “maize agroecosystems across its range”. To clarify we have added the word distribution range as follow in Line 150 of the revised manuscript: “ maize agroecosystems across its **distribution** range”.

31. what this means? it was new biotypes or what???

Response: The reviewer refers to the phrase ‘Its evolutionary expansion’ in Line 150. This phrase is referring to the evolutionary relationship between Dalbulus Spp. and Zea spp., just as the full phrase states from Line 150 to 152: “Its evolutionary expansion is thought to have occurred alongside the domestication and spread of *Z. mays* from its wild teosinte ancestors [39].”

[39] Medina RF, Reyna SM, Bernal JS. Population genetic structure of a specialist leafhopper on Zea: likely anthropogenic and ecological determinants of gene flow. Entomol Exp Appl 2012;142:223–235.

32. eliminate the personalization (this was a persistent comment throughout the manuscript)

Response: Please see point 3 of the section comments from the pdf file.

33. please define how one strain was selected as representative and representative of what?

Response: This comment is referring to the phrase ‘one representative’ in Line 161. The phrase continues from Line 161 to 162 ‘one representative sample collected each year’. Is hard to explain this very clear phrase. We didn’t change anything in the revised manuscript.

34. of course it was existing you mean sequenced may be???

Response: Referring to the phrase “with existing 16S rRNA [KT444671]” in Line 163. To avoid confusing we removed ‘with existing’. It reads now in Line 163: “16S rRNA [KT444671]”.

35. GenBank accession number

Response: Reviewer is referring to place this in front of the actual number. We corrected this as follows from Line 165 to 166: “The samples analyzed were MBS-Ver14 (previously identified as NMBS-V41 [7], 16S rRNA [[GenBank accession number](#) KT444671] and *cpn60* [[GenBank accession number](#) KT444673] sequences), MBS-Ver15, and MBS-Ver16, corresponding to collections from 2014, 2015, and 2016, respectively.”

36. Italic

Response: referring to ‘loci’ in Line 169. Done as suggested.

37. the author ignore a 2011 publication demonstrating also seed transmission in corn of 16SrI-B phytoplasmas so revise the sentence

Response: The reviewer is referring to this phrase from lines 172 to 174: “These results confirmed not only the continued presence of MBS phytoplasma in Veracruz across multiple years but also suggested ongoing reproduction and persistence of local vector populations.”

We do not understand what the reviewer means or what reference they are alluding to. After 30 minutes searching online, we believe this is what the reviewer might be referring to:

- Mitrović, J., Kakizawa, S., Duduk, B., Oshima, K., Namba, S., & Bertaccini, A. (2011). The groEL gene as an additional marker for finer differentiation of ‘Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris’-related strains. *Annals of Applied Biology*, 159, 41–48.

As we mentioned in point 9, we never stated that corn cannot be affected by other phytoplasmas; however, MBSP has only been reported in the Americas, and we provided the pertinent information proving this.

38. provide the GenBank accession numbers for these strains

Response: The reviewer is referring to ‘MBS and MBS-Col’ in Line 171. This was added as requested. See in Line 171 to 172 of revised manuscript: “_MBS ([GenBank accession number](#) AY264858) and MBS-Col ([GenBank accession number](#) AB599712).”

39. Scratched out text by reviewer: “key taxonomic markers” in Line 176 to 177 and “commonly used” in Line 175.

Response: We kept this text as it was in the revised manuscript.

40. how can these markers determine the origin a a phytoplasma strain? literature stating this must be added if available or the statment must be eliminated

Response: Refers to Line 181: “Although these sequences confirmed the presence of MBSP, they lacked sufficient phylogenetic resolution to determine the origin of the strains.” We understand the phrase can be confusing, but it means to separate the strains by geographic origin. This was corrected as follows in Line 181: “Although these sequences confirmed the presence of MBSP, they lacked sufficient phylogenetic resolution **to differentiate the strains based on their geographical origin.**”

41. Insect

Response: Added to vector in Line 183: ‘**insect** vector’.

42. ‘Taxonomic’ scratched out in line 186.

Response: It was kept in the revised manuscript (Line 188).

43. of what? please clarify

Response: Refers to ‘core-nt database’ in Line 189 of the revised manuscript. The full phrase is: “Taxonomic classification was performed with Kraken2 v.2.1.3 [48] against the core-nt database.”

Just for the reviewer understanding, but nothing to do in the text because this is a well-known and well-validated approach: Kraken2 v.2.1.3 is a taxonomic classification tool that assigns sequencing reads to known taxa by comparing short k-mers against a curated reference database. The core-nt database is a reduced, high-quality subset of the NCBI nucleotide database (nt), containing only well-annotated and non-redundant sequences. Using this compact curated database accelerates read classification while reducing false positives from low-quality or unverified sequences.

44. ??? this imply contamination from manipulation

Response: This is the reaction to the word human among the examples of possible contaminants that could be found among the reads. Nothing to do here, it is just an example. Full phrase from Line 189 to 192: “To eliminate host-derived reads (e.g., from leafhoppers, humans, and plants), we used KrakenTools v.1.2 (<https://github.com/jenniferlu717/KrakenTools>).”

45. the origin of the two sequenced strain should be better reported then

Response: Refers to “potentially reflecting adaptations to different hosts or environments” in Line 214 to 215. Is not clear to us what this means. If it is the origin of the samples, that information was clearly presented in the manuscript and also in supplementary Table S2. In the revised manuscript this can be

found from Line 181 to 189: “Motivated by our recent detection of *D. maidis* in Québec, Canada, the northernmost record to date [37], we sought to investigate: (i) whether MBSP had been introduced to this new geographic area by its insect vector, and (ii) if so, whether the local strain could be traced to known populations, particularly from the USA and Brazil. Genomic DNA was extracted as previously described [46], from insect and plant tissue (Table S2) and preparation of Illumina short-read libraries and subsequent sequencing were performed by Genome Québec (Montréal, Canada), resulting in five paired-end (PE) files of 215 M (BR), 44 M (QC), 113 M (OK), 282 (IA) and 171 M (MO) reads, respectively (Table S2).”

46. not very close in reality

Response: Refers to Line 223 to 224: “, clearly distinct from other closely related species such as ‘*Ca. P. pruni*’ and ‘*Ca. P. mali*’ (Figure 3).” In Figure 3 below is clear than after ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ cluster, these species are the next monophyletic group. We did not change anything in the revised manuscript.

Figure 3. Phylogenomic tree based on concatenated single-copy orthologous genes from all available ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma*’ genomes. The tree was inferred using maximum likelihood with bootstrap values shown at each node. Strains of ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ (MBSP-IA, MBSP-OK, MBSP-BR, and MBSP-M3)

clustered within a well-supported monophyletic clade alongside 'Ca. P. asteris' and 'Ca. P. tritici', forming a subgroup within the 16Srl lineage. The tree was rooted with *Acholeplasma laidlawii* PG-8A as outgroup. Bootstrap support values $\geq 95\%$ indicate high confidence in branching patterns.

47. the ribosomal group differentiation is not a taxonomic feature but only a useful tool for preliminary screening and only the 'Ca. Phytoplasma' species must be used for comparison

Response: Refers to Line 225 to 226: "This topology supports their classification within the 16Srl group while highlighting genomic divergence from other members."

In every single article describing a new taxon, phylogenetic analyses are essential. We disagree with the reviewer and will not perform any change in the revised manuscript. We can list all the following references that include phylogenetic analyses:

- Valdez-López, J. L., Palafox-Leal, N. L., Santos-Lopez, G., Fantino, E. I., Mohammadi, S., Levesque, R. C., Méndez-Lozano, J., Mora-Zamudio, C. I., Rodríguez-Negrete, E. A., Santos-Cervantes, M. E., Pérez-López, E., & Leyva-López, N. E. (2026). *Pectobacterium sinaloense* sp. nov., a novel phytopathogenic species isolated from potato plants in Mexico. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 76(2). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.007076>
- Pérez-López, E., Omar, A. F., Al-Jamhan, K. M., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2018). *Molecular identification and characterization of the new 16SrIX-J and cpn60 UT IX-J phytoplasma subgroup associated with chicory bushy stunt disease in Saudi Arabia*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 68(2). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.002530>
- Omar, A. F., Aljmhan, K. A., Alsohim, A. S., & Pérez-López, E. (2018). *Potato purple top disease associated with the novel subgroup 16SrII-X phytoplasma*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 68(11). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.003033>
- Pérez-López, E., Olivier, C. Y., Luna-Rodríguez, M., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2016). *Phytoplasma classification and phylogeny based on in silico and in vitro RFLP analysis of cpn60 universal target sequences*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 66(12). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.001501>
- Pérez-López, E., Luna-Rodríguez, M., Olivier, C. Y., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2016). *The underestimated diversity of phytoplasmas in Latin America*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 66(1). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.000726>
- Perez-Lopez, E., Vincent, C., Moreau, D., Hammond, C., Town, J., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2018). *A novel 'Candidatus Phytoplasma asteris' subgroup 16Srl-(E/AI)AI associated with blueberry stunt disease in eastern Canada*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 69(2). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.003100>
- Pérez-López, E., & Dumonceaux, T. J. (2016). *Detection and identification of the heterogeneous novel subgroup 16SrXIII-(A/I)I phytoplasma associated with strawberry green petal disease and Mexican periwinkle virescence*. *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*, 66(11). <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.001365>
- Naderali, N., Nejat, N., Vadamalai, G., Davis, R. E., Wei, W., Harrison, N. A., Kong, L., Kadir, J., Tan, Y.-H., & Zhao, Y. (2017). *'Candidatus Phytoplasma wodyetiae', a new taxon associated with yellow decline disease of foxtail palm (Wodyetia bifurcata) in Malaysia*. *International Journal of*

Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology, 67, 3765–3772.
<https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.002187>

- Arocha, Y., López, M., Piñol, B., Fernández, M., Picornell, B., Almeida, R., Palenzuela, I., Wilson, M. R., & Jones, P. (2005). 'Candidatus Phytoplasma graminis' and 'Candidatus Phytoplasma caricae', two novel phytoplasmas associated with diseases of sugarcane, weeds and papaya in Cuba. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 55, 2451–2463. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijms.0.63797-0>
- Zhao, Y., Wei, W., Davis, R. E., Lee, I.-M., & Bottner-Parker, K. D. (2021). *The agent associated with blue dwarf disease in wheat represents a new phytoplasma taxon, 'Candidatus Phytoplasma tritici'*. **International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology**, 71, 004604. <https://doi.org/10.1099/ijsem.0.004604>

48. there are approved threshold that must be applied to assess this not just looking ut please verify better there is no such possibility at all

Response: Refers to Lines 228-229: “ MBSP strains are clearly distinct from ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’, despite close sequence similarity (**Figure 4**).”

We are not aware of any established bootstrap threshold values. However, even though the bootstrap support is 99 for other closely related strains such as ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ and ‘*Ca. P. lycopersici*’, ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and ‘*Ca. P. zea*’-related strains cluster independently in the phylogenetic tree presented in Figure 4. We did not change the text in the revised manuscript.

Figure 4. Phylogenetic tree based on full-length 16S rRNA gene sequences from ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma*’ species, including the newly sequenced ‘*Ca. P. zeaе*’ strains (MBSP-M3, MBSP-IA, MBSP-BR, and MBSP-OK). The tree was constructed using maximum likelihood and rooted with *Acholeplasma laidlawii* PG-8A as outgroup. The 16Srl clade, to which ‘*Ca. P. zeaе*’ and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ belong, is shaded in gray. Bootstrap values (>95%) are shown at the nodes, indicating the robustness of each branch. This analysis confirms the close relationship between ‘*Ca. P. zeaе*’ and other members of the 16Srl group, while also supporting its divergence from other phytoplasma species.

49. there is no formal description for this taxon only provisional descriptions please revise

Response: The word 'formally' was removed in Line 231.

50. what is this ????

Response: the reviewer refers to "distinct nucleotide patterns" in Line 232. To avoid confusion this was changed to "unique nucleotide sequences", in Line 234.

51. ??? not real in the sequences

Response: The reviewer is referring to the phrase in Line 234: "specific diagnostic regions within the 16S rRNA gene [10]". Unless the reviewer provides more elements is impossible for us to fight facts.

52. inappropriate reference

Response: The reference is 9. Changed in Line 234: "[9]".

[9] Lee IM, Gundersen-Rindal DE, Davis RE, Bottner KD, Marccone C et al. '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma asteris', a novel phytoplasma taxon associated with aster yellows and related diseases. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;54:1037–1048.

53. Reviewer scratched "polymorphic sites" and suggested "SNPs" in Line 235.

Response: The suggestion is not correct, and we didn't change anything in the revised manuscript.

54. so it could also be '*Ca. P. tritici*' if you follow revised guidelines as you should have done

Response: This comment shows even less understanding of phytoplasma taxonomy than we thought. Is referring to Line 235 to 236: "identity with '*Ca. P. tritici*' (98.82%)".

Extracted directly from the guidelines the reviewer says we didn't review:

'*Ca. P. tritici*': Recently described from wheat in China [45]. The reference strain WBD has 98.68%–99.93% sequence identity compared with 434 '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains; therefore it does not have the required threshold to be described as species based on the 16S rRNA gene. The proposal of this new taxon was based on its unique vectorship, a distinctive symptomatology in its predominant plant host, and <95% genome-wide ANI identity compared to several '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains.

So, no. This species needs to be associated to a specific host and vectored by an specific insect. We did not change anything in the revised manuscript.

We also reference the guidelines in the original submission:

Reference 17: Bertaccini A, Arocha-Rosete Y, Contaldo N, Duduk B, Fiore N et al. Revision of the '*Candidatus* Phytoplasma' species description guidelines. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2022;72.

55. as for all bacteria threshold is 98.65% for these ones

Response: Yes, we ment all bacteria but changed to phytoplasma as suggested. Line 237: “(>98.65%)”.

56. in the cited references there is not mention of minimal set of genes for this

Response: We removed the word minimal in Line 245: “Although *rpoB* is not part of the IRPCM-recognized set for ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ classification,”.

57. too high to be accepted for new taxon

Response: Referring to ANI values in Line 260. Please see point 8. This value changed in Line 260: “92.6–98.4%”.

58. the vector is not exclusive for this bacterium

Response: The reviewer is referring to Line 266 to 267, “its specific insect vector.” This comment does not apply because we are not stating that this vector can only transmit ‘*Ca. P. zae*’, but rather that ‘*Ca. P. zae*’ can only be transmitted by *Dalbulus* spp.

59. one continent is not restricted distribution

Response: This was addressed in Point 20. We strongly disagree with this statement. “Restricted distribution” in taxonomy and epidemiology refers to ecological or biogeographical limitation. A taxon confined exclusively to one continent is, by definition, geographically restricted. This is precisely the case for ‘*Ca. P. zae*’, which has only been detected in the Americas despite more than 80 years of intensive global surveillance for phytoplasmas in corn, grasses, and leafhoppers.

Examples of continent-restricted organisms in the Americas:

- Monarch butterfly (*Danaus plexippus*), native range restricted to the Americas
- Nine-banded armadillo (*Dasypus novemcinctus*), native to the Americas
- *Phytophthora sojae*, soybean root and stem rot pathogen
- *Dalbulus maidis*, the corn leafhopper
- *Candidatus Liberibacter americanus*, restricted to the Americas
- *Trypanosoma cruzi*, Chagas disease pathogen

60. may provide some

Response: The reviewer did this in Line 264: “~~provide strong~~ support” and provided the comment above. Please refer to points 8 and 25, and we encourage a more careful reading of the article.

61. strain

Response: The reviewer scratched out the word species. We kept the original submission.

62. missing appropriate literature for this

Response: Referring to Line 265 to 266: “This interpretation aligns with the ecological species criterium, which is particularly useful when genomic metrics such as ANI and AAI approach the thresholds for species delimitation.”. We added references 12 and 17 from Line 265 to 268: “Despite the relatively limited sequence divergence among these taxa, ANI values <95% with multiple ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strains, the distinct ecological traits of ‘*Ca. P. zea*’, including its specific insect vector, narrow host range, and geographically restricted distribution, provide strong support for its recognition as a separate species [12,17].”

[12] IRPCM. ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma*’, a taxon for the wall-less, non-helical prokaryotes that colo-nize plant phloem and insects. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004;54:1243–1255.

[17] Bertaccini A, Arocha-Rosete Y, Contaldo N, Duduk B, Fiore N et al. Revision of the ‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma*’ species description guidelines. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2022;72.

63. NO

Response: Refers to this phrase in Line 269: “justify its delineation as a new taxon.”. I think after 4 comments before pdf and 62 in the pdf to this moment, we have proved that YES.

64. are not substantiated by the scientific data available

Response: The reviewer is talking about this in Line 268: “consistent biological, geographic”. We respectfully disagree; it does.

65. now the politic represent a basis for scientific recognition? big progress !!!!!

Response: The reviewer is referring to this in Line 269 to 273: “The authors proposing this classification represent a broad coalition of researchers who have studied maize bushy stunt phytoplasma for over a decade in Brazil, Colombia, Mexico, and the United States, together with a new generation of scientists working directly with growers, industry, stakeholders, and policymakers. This collective expertise and engagement lend strong support to the formal recognition of ‘*Ca. P. zea*’.”

I hope I never become bitter and cynical like this reviewer. People like you can kill love for science. There is no political statement in this section of the manuscript.

66. what is this???? authors are self referencing???? is this new type of science????

Response: This person is referring to: “and the consensus from the community represented by the authors” from Line 278 to 279. This is not self-referencing, so nothing to do in this point. Nothing to say about the second question.

67. or nucleotides??? were these verified with all the available phytoplasmas at least sequenced in this gene???

Response: Unique regions was changed by **unique nucleotides sequences** in Lines 284 to 285 of the revised manuscript. Can't understand the second question. All the pertinent information is presented in Table 1.

68. number

Response: Number was added in line 284: "(Genome GenBank accession **number** SAMN50092827)"

69. this was taken into account???

Response: Refers to reference number 2: Maramorosch K. The occurrence of two distinct types of corn stunt in Mexico. Plant Dis Rep 1955;39:896–898.

How the reviewer suggest we could take this into account? This study is from 1955 and no sequence is available. Is not clear after reading it if the authors are talking about phytoplasma or Spiroplasma.

70. update literature is available now for Peru

Response: Reviewer refers to reference number 4: Hodgetts J, Chuquillangui C, Muller G, Arocha Y, Gamarra D et al. Surveys reveal the occurrence of phytoplasmas in plants at different geographical locations in Peru. Ann Appl Biol 2009;155:15–27.

MBSP has not been reported in Peru. Infected corn plants by phytoplasma have been reported in Peru. Not the same.

71. Lee IM by Lee I-M in References 8 and 9.

Response: Changed as suggested.

72. wrong fonts please revise

Response: It was the same font.

73. Ranmsitting

Response: This is in Figure 1 legend. We didn't change anything.

74. program???

Response: The program used to perform the phylogenetic analyses was provided in the main text. No need to repeat this information in Figure 3 legend.

75. There were some things in italic that should not be. The reviewer went one by one and left a comment "not italic", this was done **11 times**.

Response: Corrected.

76. not pertinent to the manuscript

Response: We consider that **Table S1** and the information presented in **Figure 1B** constitute key evidence, evidence that this reviewer has neglected and attempted to strongly dismiss through unsupported statements and unfounded theories.

77. not clear why these references are here and not in the main text

Response: This reference support the disease and vector distribution. It was not necessary to cite it in the main text, but yes in the supplementary table.

In conclusion, we acknowledge the very substantial effort you invested in this review, including 165 individual comments and edits on the annotated PDF. We carefully considered each of them. However, despite the large volume of criticisms, only minimal changes were ultimately required in the revised manuscript, as relatively few suggestions were both constructive and compatible with current knowledge and practice in phytoplasma taxonomy and genomics. **Our core data, analytical framework, and main conclusions remain unchanged.**

That said, your review did push us to spend an entire month re-examining the literature in depth, revisiting the historical and revised '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species guidelines, and refining our understanding of why '*Candidatus Phytoplasma zae*' qualifies as a distinct taxon. This process has strengthened our grasp of phytoplasma taxonomy and sharpened the scientific rationale underlying our proposal. **For that, we are genuinely grateful, even if we strongly disagree with the tone and many of the interpretations expressed in your report.**

Reviewer 2:

As maize bushy stunt phytoplasma (MBSP) showed a 16S rRNA gene sequence identity > 99.8% compared with '*Ca. P. asteris*', the description of the new species '*Ca. Phytoplasma zae*' is based on the application of the "Rule c" of IRPCM guidelines (published in IJSEM in 2004) stating that "if 16S rRNA gene sequence identity threshold is not satisfied, a new '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species can be proposed if there is evidence that the organism represents an ecologically distinct population, demonstrated by differences in insect vectors, plant hosts, and supporting molecular divergence".

In the IRPCM guidelines (2004) this "supporting molecular diversity" was not defined, leaving its meaning to the free interpretation of the scientists and leading to some taxonomic confusion and publication of unappropriated '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species. For that reason and considering the availability of several phytoplasma genomes, in 2022, Bertaccini and colleagues published in IJSEM revised guidelines for '*Candidatus Phytoplasma*' species description. Such guidelines were approved by the International Committee on Systematics of Prokaryotes (ICSP) - Subcommittee on the taxonomy of Mollicutes. These guidelines stated that "For assigning novel '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species it is necessary that the phytoplasma has the whole 16S rRNA gene sequence with identity <98.65%". Again: "For those '*Ca. Phytoplasma*' species with 16S rRNA gene sequence identities >98.65%, the following threshold values based on average nucleotide identity (ANI) (if the genome is available) or other housekeeping genes should be used to support the effective distinction: 95% for ANI; 97.5% for *tufB* and *rpIV-rpsC* genes, 95.7% for *secA* gene and 95.0% for *secY* gene, and 97.6% for *groEL* gene". These threshold values,

indicated by Bertaccini and colleagues (2022), defined the "supporting molecular diversity", originally proposed in IRPCM guidelines (2004), using "standard" parameters to give uniformity in the description of new 'Ca. Phytoplasma' species.

The original "Rule c" needs that the organism represents ecologically distinct population, demonstrated by differences in insect vectors, plant hosts, and supporting molecular divergence. Even if the organism has specific insect vectors, plant hosts, and typical/unique geographic distribution, the "distinct population" needs to be supported by molecular divergence. Such divergence should be defined measuring the threshold values proposed by Bertaccini and colleagues (2022), using "standard" parameters to avoid confusion in phytoplasma taxonomy.

In the case of 'Ca. Phytoplasma zaeae', you proved its molecular divergence using MBSP-specific single nucleotide polymorphisms in molecular marker genes and MBSP clustering in pangenome phylogenetic analyses, an approach not indicated in the revised guidelines. It looks like you utilized these arbitrary parameters because, using the threshold values of ANI and molecular markers (as indicated in the revised guidelines), it is not possible to describe the new 'Ca. Phytoplasma zaeae'.

In fact, in the manuscript, you reported that maize bushy stunt phytoplasmas, in comparison with 'Ca. P. asteris', showed (i) ANI values of 97.7-98% (higher than ANI threshold of 95%, established in the guidelines); (ii) sequence identity of 100% and 99.4% respectively for rpl22 (rplV) and rps3 (rpsC) genes (higher than rplV-rpsC gene threshold of 97.5%, established in the guidelines); (iii) secY gene sequence identity of 99.44% (higher than secY gene threshold of 95%, established in the guidelines); (iv) secA gene sequence identity of 99.36% (higher than secA gene threshold of 95.7%, established in the guidelines); (v) groEL (cpn60UT) gene sequence identity of 99.81% (higher than groEL gene threshold of 97.6%, established in the guidelines). It is evident that 'Ca. P. zaeae' can not represent a "distinct population" because, based on ANI and marker gene sequence identity values, it is not "molecularly divergent" in comparison with 'Ca. P. asteris'. Thus, based on the data provided in the manuscript, MBSP must be considered as a member of 'Ca. P. asteris'.

Response: Thank you for agreeing to review the manuscript. We have examined the comments carefully and performed additional analyses that further support the delineation of 'Candidatus Phytoplasma zaeae' as a new taxon. This was addressed multiple times in our response to Reviewer 1, but we expand on it again here for Reviewer 2:

The evidence supporting the designation of a new species, which is based primarily on Rule c of the IRPCM guidelines (IRPCM 2004), still valid despite the 2022 updates (Bertaccini et al. 2022). Now, what is Rule c? Below we copy the relevant section directly from the 2004 manuscript:

(c) There are, however, cases of phytoplasmas that share >97.5% (in 2022 changed to 98.65%) of their 16S rRNA gene sequence, but clearly represent ecologically separated populations and, therefore, may deserve description as separate species. For such cases, description of two different species is recommended only when all three of the following conditions apply:

- (i) the two phytoplasmas are transmitted by different vectors;

- (ii) the two phytoplasmas have a different natural plant host (or, at least, their behaviour is significantly different in the same plant host);
- (iii) there is evidence of significant molecular diversity, achieved by either hybridization to cloned DNA probes, serological reaction or PCR-based assay.

How does this apply to ‘*Ca. P. zea*’?

- (i) There have been established a great diversity of leafhoppers able to transmit ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’. However, only leafhoppers into the genus *Dalbulus*, are able to transmit ‘*Ca. P. zea*’. This was very detailed from Line 120-135:

“*Dalbulus* (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) is a Neotropical genus comprising eleven recognized species, all specialized in corn (*Z. mays*), related teosintes (*Zea* spp.), or *Tripsacum* spp. as host plants [26,27]. Among these, *D. maidis* (**Figure 1B**) and *D. elimatus* (Ball) are the most prominent, feeding on both maize and teosintes [26,27]. Other species such as *D. gelbus*, *D. longulus*, and *D. guevarai* are associated with maize and/or *Tripsacum* spp., whereas *D. quinquenotatus*, *D. guvnani*, *D. chiapensis*, *D. gramalotes*, *D. charlesi*, and *D. tripsacoides* are associated exclusively with *Tripsacum* spp. [27].

Although experimental studies have shown that other *Dalbulus* species and leafhoppers from different genera (e.g., *Graminella nigrifrons* Forbes) can acquire and transmit MBSP under controlled conditions, only *D. maidis*, commonly known as the corn leafhopper, and *D. elimatus*, known as the Mexican corn leafhopper, are confirmed natural vectors [10,28-30]. Recently in Brazil, the invasive planthopper *Leptodelphax maculigera* (Stål) (Hemiptera: Delphacidae) was found to be simultaneously infected with MBSP, maize rayado fino virus and maize striate mosaic virus [31, 32]. However, further laboratory experiments indicated that this species is not a vector of the MBSP, and pearl millet (*Pennisetum glaucum*) is its primary host, rather than maize [33]. These aspects highlight a high degree of vector specificity in the transmission ecology of MBSP.”

- (ii) It is clearly established in the literature that ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ specifically affects corn and other plants within the genus *Zea*. This was presented in the original manuscript from lines 110 to 118.

“Maize bushy stunt (MBS) was first detected on corn plants in Mexico over six decades ago [2]. The main symptoms of MBS include chlorotic striping on the leaves, foliar reddening and yellowing, stunted growth, lateral branching along the stalk, deformed or poorly filled ears, and a characteristic bushy appearance [22,23]. These symptoms are consistently observed in both commercial hybrids and native landraces of maize [7,10] (**Figure 1A**). Crop losses attributed to MBS phytoplasma infection can range from 35% to as high as 93%, depending largely on the prevalence of the insect vectors and timing of the infection [24,25]. Although other members of the genus *Zea* have been shown experimentally to be susceptible to MBS phytoplasma, *Z. mays* remains the only confirmed natural host [10].”

- (iii) Yes, there is significant evidence that ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ is molecularly divergent enough from previously delineated ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species as presented in the revised manuscript from Line 232 to 264:

“Pairwise identity analysis of 16S rRNA genes revealed > 99.8% identity between MBSP and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’, but <98.65% identity with other described ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species. While MBSP and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ share specific diagnostic regions within the 16S rRNA gene [9], **unique nucleotide sequences** were observed in ‘*Ca. P. zea*’-related strains (**Table 1**). Eleven polymorphic sites differentiated ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ from ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’, notably at positions 1319–1321, 1367–1369, and 151–153 (**Table 1**). The 16S rRNA gene showed >99% identity between ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’, but lower identity with ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ (98.82%) and ‘*Ca. P. lycopersici*’ (96.71%). Given the subtle differences and high 16S similarity (threshold for species delineation has been set at >98.65%), we examined additional conserved genes for improved resolution.

Among the protein-coding genes analyzed, *rpoB* and *rps3* provided the best discriminatory power (**Table 1**). Nucleotide identity values for ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ vs. ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ were 99.31% (*rpoB*) and 99.34% (*rps3*), while identity dropped to 95.93% and 96.17%, respectively, when compared to ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’. The *rpoB* gene contained five distinct nucleotide differences (e.g., at positions 1268–1270 and 2850–2852), while *rps3* presented six (e.g., 17–19 and 570–572) (**Table 1**). Although *rpoB* is not part of the IRPCM-recognized set for ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ classification, it has been successfully used to distinguish closely related ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ strains [42,61]. The analysis of the *cpn60OUT* revealed three SNPs at positions 61, 394, and 1075, supporting its continued relevance in phylogenetic classification schemes, even though we did not detect the polymorphism at position 125 previously reported for MBS-Ver [62]. The *secY* and *secA* genes also demonstrated high identity (99.4% and 99.3%, respectively, vs. ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’) but showed lower similarity with ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ (~95.9%), each with nine informative differences.

Pangenome analysis reinforced these findings. Among 3,720 identified gene clusters (GCs), 276 were shared across all strains (core GCs), while 45 accessory GCs were exclusive to ‘*Ca. P. zea*’. Among the accessory gene clusters, we identified genes associated with amino acid transport and metabolism (15 genes), defense mechanisms (8 genes), and posttranslational modification, protein turnover, and chaperones (2 genes). A substantial fraction (137 genes) lacked functional annotation (**Table S5**). The pangenome clustering based on shared gene clusters content aligned with the phylogenetic patterns, with ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ grouping alongside ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ and ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ (**Figure 5A**). ANI analyses confirmed this relationship, showing **92.6–98.4% identity** between ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and **all available genomes for ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strains**, and 93.3–93.4% between ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ (**Figure 5B-C, Table S6, Figure S1**). AAI analyses revealed a similar pattern: ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ shared high similarity, with AAI values ranging from 96.65% to 96.88%, whereas ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ exhibited lower values, between 91.62% and 91.90% (**Table S7**).”

The newly updated criteria do not totally override previously established criteria. As stated clearly in Bertaccini et al. (2022): “The revised guidelines support all the previously assigned ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species, except four that must be adjusted to fit the revised guidelines. Previous International Research Programme on Comparative Mycoplasmaology guidelines [1] should be followed if relevant for a complete description of the new ‘*Ca. Phytoplasma*’ species when not conflicting with the present revised guidelines.”

[1] IRPCM. *Candidatus Phytoplasma*, a taxon for the wall-less, non-helical prokaryotes that colonise plant phloem and insects. *Int J Syst Evol Microbiol* 2004; 54:1243–1255.

The key part of this extract is “**when not conflicting with the present revised guidelines**”. Based on the way we presented our results and conducted the analyses, it may initially appear that our delineation conflicts with the revised thresholds:

“The new thresholds include a 16S rRNA gene sequence identity of 98.65 %, a genome ANI of 95 %, and two among five suggested housekeeping genes. For example, if the 16S rRNA gene sequence identity

for a given phytoplasma is <98.65 %, there is no need to check other sequences. If the 16S rRNA gene sequence identity is >98.65 % and the genome ANI is <95 %, checking other genes is not required. Housekeeping genes should be used when 16S rRNA gene sequence identities are >98.65 % and the whole genome sequence is unavailable.”

We initially compared ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ genomes strictly with the ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ reference genome (GCA_038505995.1), obtaining an ANI of 97.7–98.0%. However, we have now expanded the analysis and compared ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ genomes with all 20 available ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’-related strain genomes in NCBI (Genbank accession numbers: GCA_038505995.1 (Ref), GCA_038396745.1, GCA_047530585.1, GCA_030686925.1, GCF_019396865.1, GCA_000012225.1, GCA_020714625.1, GCA_004214875.1, GCA_041920595.1, GCA_047530585.1, GCA_036985145.1, GCA_001866375.1, GCA_018283495.1, GCA_002554195.1, GCA_000744065.1, GCA_000803325.1, GCA_000009845.1, GCA_013372025.1, GCA_003181115.1, GCA_005093185.1), finding **<95% genome-wide ANI identity** relative to 4 of the ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ strains (See new revised **Table S6** and the new **Figure S1**).

The four ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ genomes presenting **<95% genome-wide ANI identity** relative to ‘*Ca. P. zea*’ have been clearly validated as 16SrI and ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ -related strains. Additionally, the quality of the sequences is optimal with several of them assembled in the last 5 years, as the references below can confirm:

References:

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- Bai, X., Correa, V. R., Toruño, T. Y., Ammar, E.-D., Kamoun, S., & Hogenhout, S. A. 2009. AY-WB phytoplasma secretes a protein that targets plant cell nuclei. *Molecular Plant-Microbe Interactions*, 22(1), 18–30. <https://doi.org/10.1094/MPMI-22-1-0018>
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- Song, S., Wang, Q., Huo, L., Xie, L., Chen, J., Cui, H., Dai, Z., Kang, J., Li, Y., Guo, W., Chen, J., Kang, L., & Zhang, X. 2025. The phytoplasma (‘*Candidatus Phytoplasma arecae*’) is the crucial pathogen causing areca palm yellow leaf disease. *Science Bulletin*, 70(6), 847–851. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scib.2024.10.020>

Is this in compliance with the 2022 guidelines? Yes. This is exactly the same situation under which ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ was accepted as a new species according to the revised guidelines.

During the delineation of ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’ Zhao et al. (2021) stated: “As shown in Table 2, the ANI scores between the WBD phytoplasma and diverse ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’ strains varied from 93.88–94.69 %, justifying the WBD phytoplasma as a new taxon separate from ‘*Ca. P. asteris*’. Taken together, these results indicate that ecological uniqueness of the WBD phytoplasma has its roots in the genome.” This might be true for the 10 strains presented in the manuscript, but we don’t know if it is the case for all the 20 genomes available.

Bertaccini et al. (2022) echoed this language during the updates of the rules regarding ‘*Ca. P. tritici*’: **“The proposal of this new taxon was based on its unique vectorship, a distinctive symptomatology in**

its predominant plant host, and <95% genome-wide ANI identity compared **to several** '*Ca. P. asteris*' strains."

Based on the comments of Reviewer 2, we can conclude that everything else was correct and the article can be accepted.

To the Editors,

Thank you again and we are very hopeful to one day seeing our manuscript accepted and published in *International Journal of Systematic and Evolutionary Microbiology*.

Sincerely,

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